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Report on pilot setup, current practices and initial requirements

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Abstract

The development of new infrastructures and assessment tools is often driven by the possibilities offered by new data sources or new technologies, rather than the needs of end users. To ensure that indicators, tools, services and infrastructure applied in assessment or monitoring are based on community needs, GraspOS includes nine pilots involving a highly diverse group of stakeholders. The pilots take part from the beginning of the project in requirement acquisition, co-design, validation, evaluation and demonstration of the indicators, tools, services and infrastructure developed. The pilots represent three different types of Open Science enabled research assessment: 1) funding agencies and national stakeholders operating infrastructure, 2) universities, including departments and research groups, and 3) thematic disciplines.

The first task of the pilots was to conduct an analysis to describe the current status of the pilot's evaluation aims, context, and resources. Furthermore, the analyses collect contextually relevant information to facilitate shaping of the pilot evaluation events focused on open science practices to support Work Package 2 (*Open Science Assessment Framework*), as well as provide information on the initial requirements and current best practices for indicators, data, tools and services to support WP3 (*Tools and services to support Open Science aware Responsible Research Assessment*) and WP4 (*Open Metrics Federated Infrastructure*). The deliverable reports on the pilot setups, their current practices and initial requirements by bringing together the main findings of the nine individual pilot analyses.

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Abbreviation List

ARC - Athena Research Center

CoARA - Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment

CNR - National Research Council of Italy

CRIS - Current Research Information System

CS - Computer Science

DORA - The San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment

EEA - European Economic Area

INRAE - National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment

INRIA - National Institute for Research in Digital Science and Technology

OA - Open Access

OPERAS - Open scholarly communication in the European research area for social sciences and humanities

OS - Open Science

RA - Research Assessment

RDI - Research, Development and Innovation

RRA - Responsible Research Assessment

SSH - Social sciences and humanities

UB - University of Belgrade

UEF - University of Eastern Finland

UEFISCDI - The Executive Unit for the Financing of Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation

UniBO - University of Bologna

UU - Utrecht University

1. Executive Summary

This report summarises the individual analyses conducted by nine pilots covering three different types of Open Science enabled research assessment: 1) funding agencies and national stakeholders operating infrastructure, 2) universities, including departments and research groups, and 3) thematic disciplines. The pilot analyses describe the current status of the pilots' evaluation aims, context, and resources, establish the pilots' ambitions and level of maturity towards research assessment reform, and collect contextually relevant information to facilitate shaping of the pilot evaluation events focused on open science practices to support WP2, as well as provide information on the initial requirements and current best practices for indicators, data, tools and services to support WP3 and WP4.

The key conclusions made based on the pilot analyses are as follows:

- the pilots represent a wide variety of stakeholders providing GraspOS an opportunity to develop indicators, tools, services and infrastructure applied in assessment or monitoring based on real community needs;
- the pilots have a shared understanding of what open science aware research assessment means, as well as of the development needs and challenges to do with new ways of evaluating or monitoring open science;
- the pilots mention international cooperation in designing mutually acceptable ways to evaluate open science, developing practices, tools, indicators and methods to allow comparisons, and developing indicators for new types of activities currently overlooked in general assessment practices as the main benefits of participating in GraspOS;
- the pilots fully support the commitments of the [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#) (also known as the CoARA Agreement)
- an outcome of the international Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)

2. Introduction

The development of new infrastructures and assessment tools is often driven by the possibilities offered by new data sources or new technologies, rather than the needs of end users. This can lead to assessment and monitoring tools that are either ignored by end users or used in research assessments despite their poor fit with the objectives of the assessment. As indicators, tools, services and infrastructure applied in assessment or monitoring should be based on community needs, GraspOS takes a user-centred approach to developing them. This is ensured by the nine participating pilots involving a highly diverse group of stakeholders from the onset into the requirement acquisition, co-design, validation, evaluation and demonstration of the indicators, tools, services and infrastructure developed.

The pilots represent evaluation or monitoring activities considering open science in three different contexts: 1) funding agencies and national stakeholders operating infrastructure, 2) research performing organisations, including departments and research groups, and 3) thematic disciplines. Within the first category, pilots supporting open science aware research assessment (OS-aware RA) for funders and national stakeholders, there are two pilots: Finland's national CRIS Research.fi run by CSC - IT Center for Science and the national funding monitoring platforms of the main research funder in Romania, UEFISCDI. Research.fi compiles information on Finnish research from institutional, national and international sources. Its purpose is to provide an overall picture and a comprehensive information base of the research produced in Finland. UEFISCDI ensures online submission and evaluation of RDI calls, online contracting, monitoring and reporting of projects and scientific progress, at both national and international levels. It supports with online platforms the whole life cycle of a project: from project submission, evaluation of the proposals to monitoring and reporting. In both countries, funders, policy makers and other stakeholders rely on national platforms to retrieve the information useful for running research assessment and monitoring open science.

Within the second category there are four pilots supporting OS-aware RA at research organisations in four countries: the Netherlands, Italy, Finland and Serbia. The Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development in Utrecht University (UU) builds on current OS monitoring activities and visions for novel forms of recognition and rewards put forward by the OS programme of the university. The Research Council of Italy (CNR) approved a "Relaunch Plan" in 2022 which includes a reform of the research assessment system. CNR

signed the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment¹ in November 2022, and as per its declared commitment, the whole apparatus and processes for assessing the career progressions of CNR researchers and technologists are deemed to change. The pilot analyses both the criteria applied in the last selection (in 2020) and instantiated in the new call (2023), and assesses how the latter takes a step away from the legacy one. University of Eastern Finland (UEF) analyses and evaluates university-level indicators and metrics of publishing activities found in the Finnish national publication information service, and tests less used indicators and metrics with the aim of being able to utilize new indicators and metrics in responsible research assessment and in monitoring open science. The institutional repository of the University of Belgrade Faculty of Chemistry (UB), Cherry, is used as a source of information for preparing annual reports listing research results. The pilot aims at developing new generation metrics based on qualitative information deriving from the Cherry Repository that can support the Faculty of Chemistry to improve its research assessment practices. The research evaluation events for these four pilots are very different. For UU, the focus is on a departmental level, for CNR the focus is on career progression, for UEF the focus is on an organisational level, and for UB it is on a Faculty level, more precisely the use of its institutional repository.

The third category supporting OS-aware RA at research communities includes three pilots in different thematic communities covering computer science, agricultural and veterinary science, and social sciences and humanities. These pilots will investigate discipline-specific data, indicators and tools that can enhance research assessment at institutional level for research performing organisations focusing on a specific thematic area. The pilot on computer science (CS), lead by INRIA, UniBO and ATHENA, will provide general assessment criteria for CS, considering the specificity of the domain: central role of conferences, wide usage of preprints in several subdomains of CS, and importance and visibility and impact through software development. The pilot on agricultural and veterinary science, led by INRAE, considers open science as engagement with different audiences, building trustworthy relationships with stakeholders, and involving stakeholders throughout the research process. INRAE supports policy makers, participatory science and research, open innovation and dissemination of all types of research findings. Assessing the engagement and impact of OS is key for the institute. The pilot on social sciences and humanities (SSH), led by OPERAS, will provide general assessment criteria for SSH, considering one specificity of the domain: the publications rather than the data (i.e. monographs, OA books, diamond OA journals and related services developed by OPERAS at EU level).

¹ [The Agreement full text - CoARA](#)

The first task of the pilots was to conduct an analysis to describe the current status of the pilot's evaluation aims, context, and resources. The analyses establish the pilots' ambitions and level of maturity towards research assessment reform. Furthermore, the analyses collect contextually relevant information to facilitate shaping of the pilot evaluation events focused on open science practices to support Work Package 2 (WP2, developing an Open Science Assessment Framework), as well as provide information on the initial requirements and current best practices for indicators, data, tools and services to support WP3 (developing tools and services to support OS-aware RA) and WP4 (developing a federated open metrics infrastructure).

This deliverable reports on the pilot setups, their current practices and initial requirements by bringing together the main findings of the nine individual pilot analyses, following the template's structure:

1. Pilots' local state of affairs
2. Evaluation context
3. Pilot ambitions.

The individual analyses are available only for project internal use.

3. Methodology

The structure and expected content of the analysis was defined by a template (Annex 1). The template was created in cooperation with WP2, WP3 and WP4 to ensure that the analyses can be utilised in the planning and development work of the aforementioned work packages. The template included three sections, one for pilots' local state of affairs, one for evaluation context and one for pilot ambitions. The template included supporting questions for each section to help in figuring out what kinds of issues could be discussed under each heading. However, it was fully appreciated that the pilots are diverse in their needs and vision, as well as in their level of maturity in relation to research assessment reform and infrastructure, so it was completely up to the pilots if they found the supporting questions relevant to answer or not.

The pilots were required to use the headings and tables provided in the template to maintain a common structure as well as support the compiling of this summary report. The pilots uploaded their individual analysis in word-format to the GraspOS Google Drive directory, where they are available for the project's internal use.

Pilots conducted their analysis using different methodologies. As an example, internal discussions within the pilot settings as well as workshops, interviews and surveys with external stakeholders were mentioned.

A GraspOS Landscape Survey for pilots to investigate current research assessment practices and to monitor the maturity of the pilot institutions in relation to CoARA was carried out simultaneously with the pilot analysis. The survey is a part of the WP2 Landscape analysis which provides an overview of the most central policies and frameworks related to OS-aware RRA, related initiatives, use and handling of quantitative indicators and qualitative input, and the current software infrastructures supporting research assessment (Hyrkkänen et al 2023, in preparation). All nine pilots answered the survey, and for CS both INRIA and UniBO responded, so the total number of responses was 10. In this report only such results of the survey that directly relate to the pilots' maturity in terms of OS-aware RRA are summarised; for full results, please see the GraspOS Deliverable 2.1: OS-aware RRA approaches landscape report (Hyrkkänen et al 2023).

4. Pilots' local state of affairs

In the first section of the pilot analysis, the pilots were asked to describe their local state of affairs in relation to open science and/or research assessment, tools, services and datasets used, and gaps in terms of tools, services and data. This section first describes the current situation in the pilots in regard to open science practices and research assessment, as well as the operational framework and environment of the pilots: how is open science and research assessment defined and which actors are influential in this space. In addition, the pilots were asked to consider what they are currently missing in terms of tools, services, or data.

4.1. Pilots supporting OS-aware RA for funders and national stakeholders

Both pilots operate on a national level, but have different roles: Research.fi is not an evaluation tool, nor is it designed for supporting evaluation. It collects and disseminates information on Finnish research and its outputs. Whereas UEFISCDI supports the whole life cycle of a research project from project submission, evaluation of the proposals to monitoring and reporting with online platforms. Currently, neither pilot considers open science practices

for research assessment. However, UEFISCDI being a national research funding agency designated by the Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitalization to define, run, and monitor research project calls, is expected to start monitoring indicators on open science practices. In addition, it intends to start considering open science practices for research assessment purposes, namely by introducing OS as an evaluation criterion for research projects as part of a pilot RDI funding programme. Research.fi acts as a platform for disseminating the results of the national monitoring of open science and research.

For both pilots, the operational framework is defined by quite recently published national level strategies, policies and recommendations on open science or research assessment. The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment is mentioned as an important development for both pilots, as well as national initiatives and ongoing developments. UEFISCDI has a dual role: in addition to being a research funder, it also acts as a policy advisor, so it is well-connected to current developments within Romania. UEFISCDI is one of the main actors at national level in regard to open science as well as research assessment. However, UEFISCDI has no legislative power and cannot make decisions without the approval of the ministry and other relevant advisory bodies.

In both countries, the relevant ministries are considered as dominant actors in the field of open science as well as research assessment. The countries also have advisory or coordinating bodies representing the scientific community in issues to do with open science or research assessment, the National Open Science and Research Coordination in Finland and the National Council for Attestation of University Titles, Diplomas and Certificates in Romania, and finally both analyses consider research funding organisations to have a dominant role in terms of both open science and research assessment.

Both pilots are currently lacking information and indicators on open science practices beyond open access publishing. UEFISCDI is also lacking a national repository for publications and data, national commitment for adhering to open science practices and incorporation of open science practices into research assessment. Research.fi is lacking information on teaching merits or software, and international researchers in Finland who do not have strong Suomi.fi identification cannot create a researcher profile.

4.2. Pilots supporting OS-aware RA at research organisations

What open science aware research assessment means, and how open science practices are considered and acknowledged in research assessment varies considerably within the four pilots supporting OS-aware RA at research organisations.

UU states in their pilot analysis that openness is recognized and rewarded in all domains. By openness they refer to sharing of data and software according to FAIR guidelines, sharing of publications by means of open access, and active involvement of societal partners and stakeholders and the general public in their academic work. Open science practices are monitored through surveys, and their results indicate that most respondents understand how a more open and transparent approach to research can increase the quality of research, but translation into practice remains a hurdle.

For CNR, in regard to career progression in which the pilot focuses on, open access availability of research outputs is considered only now, in the latest ongoing selection where OA status is a mandatory information for outputs in the applicants' portfolios. However, it is not known at the time of writing this analysis if and how this information will be evaluated. The portfolio also includes non-literature research outputs, encompassing a broad range of diverse products and activities, but the decision on if and how to evaluate certain CV-titles (such as data/software sharing/deposition) is up to each individual selection committee.

UEF has set three strategic targets related to open science considering a) data management and FAIR principles, b) open access to all publications, and c) strengthening impact of research through diverse science communication. For all three targets, the services to support realising these aims have been strengthened. The organisation-level research assessments conducted regularly consider a wide variety of outputs and processes, including merits in open science. But the targets of assessment, research communities are fairly free to decide which elements of their research activity they wish to highlight in their self-assessments (primary assessment material).

Finally, the UB Faculty of Chemistry, the institutional repository of which, Cherry, is the fourth pilot in this category, is currently in a situation where research assessment is realised through the national evaluation system, which is solely based on the impact factors of the Journal Citation Report and Scimago Journal & Country Rank.

The operational framework for the four pilots is defined to some extent by national level strategies and programmes, it is clear that open science as well as responsible research assessment is high on national science policy agendas. But for pilots supporting OS RA at universities and research performing organisations an even more important framework

seems to come from institutional strategies and policies, like UU's Strategic plan 2025² and their Open Science Programme³, the CNR Roadmap for Open Science⁴ and the CNR Piano per Riorganizzazione e rilancio⁵ (The CNR plan for the reorganisation and relaunch), UEF's Strategy 2030⁶, and UB's Rulebook on Open Science⁷. In addition, all pilots consider the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment⁸ as influential in current developments. The operational environment of the four pilots focuses mainly on institutional-level developments, where they have access to developing and reforming research assessment practices. Also, the dominant actors defining open science and research assessment for the pilots are mainly institutional level actors, like the Open Science Platform in UU, or the UEF working group on open science.

Currently, UU is lacking full registration of all kinds of activities and outputs, full deposit of all full text of UU outputs in the repository with the option to facilitate mining and NLP, altmetrics data in the repository and data on code sharing and data sharing. CNR lacks a centralised application system where to build a CV and portfolio, and the manual operation of reporting indicators seems trivial. There is no clear indication on how impact is going to be evaluated, and the criteria for the selections are not available beforehand. UEF has very robust information content, they do however mention missing some global data sources and tools, such as Altmetric.com or SciVal, but the need for these tools has not been considered big enough to justify the high costs of altmetric data sources. UB mentions the lack of alternative metrics through which additional practices for responsible research assessment could be established.

4.3. Pilots supporting OS-aware RA for thematic disciplines

The three pilots supporting open science aware research assessment for thematic disciplines come from different perspectives. The pilot on Computer Science is run by three institutions:

² <https://www.uu.nl/sites/default/files/UtrechtUniversity-StrategicPlan2025.pdf>

³ [Utrecht University Open Science Programme 2018-2021](#)

⁴ <https://publications.cnr.it/api/v1/documents/download/198330> (available in Italian)

⁵ [Approvazione del Piano di Riorganizzazione e Rilancio | Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche](#) (closed access)

⁶ [Strategy 2030 | University of Eastern Finland](#)

⁷ Full text (only available in Serbian): <https://cherry.chem.bg.ac.rs/handle/123456789/5990>; Draft version in English: <https://cherry.chem.bg.ac.rs/handle/123456789/5991>

⁸ [The Agreement full text - CoARA](#)

the National Institute for Research in Digital Science and Technology (INRIA, FR), University of Bologna (Unibo, IT) and Athena Research Center (ARC, GR), covering a wide range of research areas from high theoretical topics to practical or experimental areas, often in a multidisciplinary context. The pilot on agricultural and veterinary science is run by the National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE, FR) and it is a mix of institutional and disciplinary pilot. While the pilot on social sciences and humanities is run by OPERAS, which is a research infrastructure supporting open scholarly communication in the SSH domain.

CS has a long-standing tradition of openness, owing in particular to the production of software which requires openness and sharing. This has led to a whole range of contributions around Open Source Software. Beside software development itself, the CS domain has been an early adopter of technologies and platforms facilitating the dissemination of research results, and it has a long-standing involvement in opening up publications. In terms of research assessment, one of the challenges being faced by the CS domain is the low coverage of publications in commercial bibliographic databases often used in evaluations. Unlike in other scientific domains, conferences and workshops are recognized as a central place for quality publications in CS, so the developments towards considering a wider range of research outputs in research assessments driven by the CoARA is in line with the expectations of the CS field, and several ICT institutions have signed the Agreement and joined the CoARA.

In INRAE, open science and scientific integrity practices have been taken into account in researcher assessment since 2020, and currently only freely accessible publications are considered in assessment. The assessment also considers data or software codes, which must be managed throughout their life cycle according to FAIR principles, as well as participatory research and science taking into account non-academic stakeholders, participatory projects, public engagement in science, etc. The researcher assessments conducted at INRAE aim at giving advice, not sanctions or rewards, and take into account a wide variety of missions and activities corresponding to personal and career paths. The fact that this pilot is also an institutional one becomes clear from the description of its operational framework and environment. Open science is defined through an institutional open science policy based on international and national documentation, its implementation is set out in an action plan, and the main actor is an institutional body, the Directorate for Open Science. Research assessment at individual level is managed by the Directorate for Assessment. INRAE is also a signatory of DORA and has made progress in applying its principles. There are several institutional level developments ongoing at INRAE to do with, for example, supporting the

recognition of INRAE's researchers commitment to open science, as well as the impact of openness on its beneficiaries.

Being a research infrastructure dedicated to open scholarly communication, OPERAS is a strong supporter of the open science policy and contributes to developing its practices. OPERAS considers research evaluation and the evolution of its methods and practices crucial to encouraging the implementation of open science. The pilot is closely linked to a project on the skills of SSH publishers from the perspective of open science, as it appears that open science practices are not implemented or rewarded in editorial skills and publication practices. OPERAS emphasises the importance of multilingual practice in research evaluation, the role of publications in ethical and responsible journals, the issue of open peer-review and the collective dimension of research work (related to DIAMAS project⁹). The operational environment for OPERAS is defined by domain specific issues to do with open science and research assessment. It is connected to a number of projects, and its main interest is in developing tools and services that can be used for assessment of open science practices, as this is the role of the infrastructure and its purpose is to build services in the framework of open science.

Within the CS domain, there is a gap in linking the existing solid open science infrastructures with general research assessment practices relying on older generation databases that do not fulfil the needs of CS at large. On a more specific level, the CS domain is lacking good cross-reference mechanisms between publication repositories and data repositories and Software Heritage, as well as automatic detection of references to data sets and software in publications. In addition, a better coverage of conferences, and a reliable and structured authority list of conferences to control the metadata used in repositories is needed.

At INRAE, in terms of monitoring open science, indicators on data FAIRness and data usage are missing, also proxy indicators for reproducibility, policy usage indicators and the ability to compare the performance between institutions, countries or disciplines is not available.

OPERAS raises the lack of information on researchers' translation activities, which is an important part of activity in the SSH domain.

⁹ [DIAMAS project](#)

5. Pilots' maturity in terms of OS-aware RRA

In terms of what kind of a role OS-aware RRA plays for the pilots, according to the survey, for most respondents (9/10) alignment with RRA as well as improving the rewarding and recognition of OS practices were the underlying motivation for participating in GraspOS. Participating in CoARA was also mentioned as motivation by most (6/10). The majority of respondents (8/10) replied that their pilot institutions are committed to national and international assessment agreements, policies or recommendations, and there is a diversity of research outputs that are taken into account in research assessment or monitoring. However, there is a lot of variation in recognition of different types of open science practices related to the research process: most pilots recognise OA publishing (7/10 respondents) and data sharing (5/10), but other practices, such as software sharing, preprints, or open peer-review only receive a few mentions. There is a lot of variation also in terms of how pilots participate in international OS monitoring activities, like for example OpenAIRE MONITOR¹⁰, the EOSC Observatory¹¹, or the monitoring framework for the UNESCO Recommendation on OS¹². In fact, 'other', indicating national level monitoring, got the most mentions (4/10) while the international options got only two or three.

The majority of pilots (6/10 respondents) considered the absence on incentivising policies of guidelines from external actors such as governments and research funders as well as the complexity of reforming research assessment caused by, for example, different national and disciplinary practices as being the main barriers and difficulties in revisiting and reforming research assessment procedures. Concerns over increased costs, lack of suitable data or metrics and alignment of institutional assessment procedures with nationally and internationally dominant procedures each got five mentions. Other issues included implementation problems, lack of coordination and lack of awareness and evidence of the benefits of reforming research assessment, with four mentions each. Also, resistance from researchers and academic leadership were mentioned by two pilot respondents.

¹⁰ [OpenAIRE | Monitor](#)

¹¹ [EOSC Observatory](#)

¹² [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#)

6. Evaluation context

The second section of the pilot analysis is about the evaluation context. This section is about explaining how evaluation (or monitoring) is situated in the local setting, and what is entailed in defining what is valued - specifically for the purpose of this project, what open science practices are valued. This section is also about explaining why an evaluation is being conducted, and for whom - who are the beneficiaries and what do they want to know. The pilots were also asked to fill in a table indicating which open practices are considered or acknowledged in evaluation or monitoring within the pilot setting. In addition, the table is used to indicate on which types of open science activity (e.g., outputs, usage, practices) data are collected within the pilot setting.

6.1. Pilots supporting OS-aware RA for funders and national stakeholders

The evaluative contexts of these two pilots are very different. While Research.fi is not an evaluation tool, nor is it designed to support evaluations, UEFISCDI is a research funding agency with a task to ensure online submission and evaluation of RDI calls as well as monitoring and reporting of projects and scientific progress. However, the functions of the researcher profile in Research.fi include enabling the transfer of information to research funders or organisations, which allows using the information for evaluation purposes.

The key stakeholders, responsible for overseeing the development of Research.fi, are represented in a steering group: research performing, funding and supporting organisations, with the Ministry of Education and Culture, the owner and funder of Research.fi, acting as chair. For UEFISCDI, the key stakeholders are the research communities as well as policy makers, and UEFISCDI itself acts as the key actor in conducting this pilot evaluation event in cooperation with the research communities represented through individual researchers and research performing organisations.

In both pilots, defining which open science practices should be valued, i.e. monitored or evaluated, is done on a national level in the form of strategies, plans, declarations and policies, in cooperation with relevant actors of the research community. According to the

White Paper on the transition to Open Science¹³, in Romania, besides raising awareness on OS practices and their benefits, the following types of actions were also identified as necessary in order for them to become embedded in mainstream research practices, as well as recognized and valued: development of necessary infrastructure and services for OS, adapting evaluation processes/ reward and recognition systems in the context of OS; ensuring transparency and fairness of costs for OA publications and for access to international publications (e.g. transformative agreements); development of capabilities necessary for the implementation of OS; ensuring open access to scientific publications resulted from publicly-funded research; and other.

In the case of Finland, monitoring open science practices in order to raise awareness of open science practices and the benefits thereof is also considered necessary, and the national monitoring of open science and research already provides a variety of indicators to Research.fi on national, sectoral and organisational level. The pilot is, however, more focused on enabling a more diverse researcher profile, including an openness profile developed in GraspOS.

Neither pilot currently considers or acknowledges open science practices in monitoring or evaluation. Data is collected on openness of publications in both pilots. In Research.fi, organisational level survey data is collected on services and policy documents on open science, research assessment and culture of open scholarship. At UEFISCDI, such data is collected for the EEA & Norway grants program¹⁴, for which it acts as a programme operator, as well as for national RDI funding programmes that it manages, but the aggregated results are not yet made publicly available.

6.2. Pilots supporting OS-aware RA at research organisations

As mentioned already in the introduction, the pilots supporting OS-aware RA at research organisations have different focus, and thus the evaluation context varies. For the purpose of

¹³ <https://uefiscdi.gov.ro/news-carte-a-alba-a-tranzitiei-catre-stiinta-deschisa-2023-2030>

¹⁴ <https://eeagrants.org/news/programme-agreement-signed-research-programme-romania>

the pilot analysis, UU focuses on the self-evaluation of research conducted as part of the SEP-evaluation (Strategy Evaluation Protocol), more specifically how open science was considered and made available for assessment in the self-assessment report. SEP provides guidelines for evaluating research and research policy in the Netherlands, and all research institutes and research groups at universities are assessed every six years according to this standardised protocol. Which elements of open science are considered in the evaluation is defined in the SEP guidelines, which are established by the Universities of the Netherlands, the Dutch Research Council and the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences.

In the case of the CNR pilot, the career progression across different levels is regulated by nation-wide selections, reserved to CNR staff. It is operated by CNR direction and head of HR, and regulated in the National Collective Labour Agreement, but the details of what should be considered in the evaluation and how, is decided in the dedicated evaluation committee of each research area. As mentioned before, even though OA status is now a mandatory information for the outputs listed in the portfolio, it is not known if and how it will be evaluated.

At UEF, research evaluations are conducted according to organisational strategic priorities and evaluation principles. Evaluation principles take into account a variety of national and international recommendations and declarations the university is committed to. All Finnish higher education institutions report on their publishing activity annually to the Ministry of Education and Culture, and publishing data is used as an indicator in the university funding model, so UEF collects and stores a wide range of information on publishing activities. The funding model defines which activities are monitored, and in the case of open science it is openness of publications. For UB, current practices for research evaluation are limited to impact factors, so the pilot is very differently situated in its local context in relation to the other pilots in this category, being an initiator of open science aware research assessment within the institution through, for example, developing an assessment protocol for in-departmental career assessment and implementing a researcher openness profile as an add-on to the local repository.

The intended stakeholders, audiences and/or beneficiaries of the four pilots vary somewhat. For UU and CNR both the evaluated and the evaluators are considered, for UEF the intended stakeholders are leaders and managers, i.e. the evaluators, and for UB the main stakeholders are researchers, i.e. the evaluated, as they are the user of the institutional repository being developed in the pilot.

Within the pilots supporting OS RA at universities and research performing organisations such open science practices as reproducibility, interdisciplinarity, research output usages and collaboration are considered or acknowledged in monitoring or evaluation. Data is collected on open research outputs, links among research outcomes, usage of research outcomes, usage of service and data on practising OS.

6.3. Pilots supporting OS-aware RA for thematic disciplines

For CS and SSH (OPERAS), the context of the pilot is about developing and supporting evaluation practices in their respective domains according to the values and practices (esp. publishing practices) inherent to their scientific fields, not conducting evaluations. Whereas for agricultural and veterinary science (INRAE) the pilot is about developing their evaluation and monitoring practices to better match institutional values; openness, interdisciplinarity, research output quality, as well as to recognize the diversity of research activities. Fittingly, the identified stakeholders and beneficiaries for the INRAE pilot are the institution and actors within the institution, researchers and the directorates for assessment and open science. For CS, it is important to ensure that making better usage of the widening of open science principles is beneficial for all levels: institutions, laboratories, research groups, funded projects, and above all, researchers. But for the sake of the pilot, researchers and institutions are priority target groups. OPERAS considers three types of stakeholders: researchers, publishers/editors involved in open access scholarly communication and research infrastructure professionals. In terms of beneficiaries, the outcomes of the pilot can serve funders and policy-makers, but also senior management in research performing organisations.

Within the pilots supporting OS-aware RA for thematic disciplines such open science practices as FAIRness, reproducibility, interdisciplinarity, research output usages and collaboration are considered or acknowledged in monitoring or evaluation. Data is collected on open research outputs, links among research outcomes, usage of research outcomes, usage of services, and data on practising open science.

7. Pilot ambitions

The third and final section of the analysis describes the pilots' ambitions in terms of developing new ways of evaluating or monitoring open science. Pilots were asked to analyse the reasons for evaluating open science, what they want to develop in this respect, and why. Lastly it was asked what the pilots think GraspOS has to offer them, and what kinds of challenges or barriers they anticipate to be involved in developing new ways of evaluating or monitoring open science.

In addition, the pilots were asked to consider how GraspOS tools, services and datasets might be helpful. This was conducted by indicating in a table prefilled with existing GraspOS components (Annex 2) which of the components could be interesting for each pilot by describing relevant use case scenarios, as well as specific requirements for the use of selected components.

7.1. Pilots supporting OS-aware RA for funders and national stakeholders

Openness of publications is an indicator in the Finnish funding model for higher education institutions. This information is collected annually, and it is available in Research.fi. In addition, Research.fi acts as a platform for presenting the results of the national monitoring of open science and research. The purpose of monitoring open science for both instances is to follow up and support the developments in open science in Finland. The results of both instances can also be used for benchmarking, and the indicators of the national monitoring of open science and research are used to determine organisations' openness profiles and their level of open science and research.

Open science practices are not currently evaluated or monitored at national level in Romania. At the moment, UEFISCDI monitors selected open science practices only as part of an EEA & Norway grants program, for which it acts as a programme operator, and collects data on openness of research publications for all programs it funds. However, UEFISCDI wishes to drive changes in the attitudes and behaviour at the level of both individual researchers and institutional actors from the RDI ecosystem, so the pilot aims to showcase contribution to open scholarship as part of researchers' CVs/profiles.

Both pilots have ambitions to expand the type of research outputs and activities to be included in researchers' profiles to obtain a more diverse and comprehensive view on the contributions researchers bring to open scholarship and science in general. For Research.fi more generally, including new information on elements of open science to do more with the research process than outputs is envisioned. However, the steering group of Research.fi raised some concerns over the ambiguous nature of open science especially in terms of how activities and merits in open science not currently available could be captured in a reliable way.

Research.fi and UEFISCDI operate on a national level within the context of open science and research assessment and are well positioned to initiate and drive change. However, cultural change required to realise the reform on research assessment has to happen globally. Therefore international cooperation is seen as the greatest added value of GraspOS. Particularly in discussing why OS should be evaluated or monitored, in designing mutually accepted ways to do that, and in supporting the implementation of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment.

For Research.fi the biggest challenge in developing new ways of evaluating or monitoring open science has to do with lack of comprehensive and reliable information. Usually, the researcher is the only one with comprehensive information on their research activities, so a primary location where to store such information is needed, and to avoid overburdening researchers, this location should be connected to existing information systems already used by them. In addition, for researchers to submit this new type of information, they need to consider it worth their while. For UEFISCDI, there are challenges related to resistance to change as well as to difficulties in ensuring data interoperability.

7.2. Pilots supporting OS-aware RA at research organisations

UU already has existing institutional processes that potentially enable rewarding diverse ways of working within academia and incentivise the production of knowledge that makes a difference in contemporary societal issues. The pilot aims at developing evaluation of open science that attends to those processes in the context of self-evaluation of researchers, self-assessment of research activities as part of SEP-evaluation, or other moments where

collective assessments of activities take place, like for example in assessing impact of research.

For CNR, it is already apparent that there is a clear ongoing transition towards the research evaluation reform, with explicit mentions of CoARA and the Agreement in the 2023 main calls, and the ground rules outlined for the 2023 selection moving towards open science and responsible research assessment. So the pilot aims through comparing the selection criteria of 2020 and 2023 calls to see how the procedure is transitioning towards the agreement, and following up if the last round of career progressions and its more diverse, and open science aware criteria sparks positive behavioural changes in CNR staff towards open science practices.

At UEF, developing research assessment is primarily motivated by aligning with responsible research assessment, participating in CoARA, and improving recognition of open science practices. They also take lead from the Ministry of Education and Culture's 2019 evaluation on maturity of openness, and especially the identified obstacles still hindering the openness of science and research in Finland. They conclude that to overcome the identified obstacles researchers' home organisations should step up in providing instructions and support services, and the pilot aims at finding solutions to overcome these obstacles.

At UB, the pilot aims at developing a reward system in the institutional repository, which could be initiated by evaluating and monitoring the use of open science through the deposition of scientific research outputs in green open access. The pilot activities realised in Cherry could in the future be adapted to other institutions that are part of the UB Computer Centre infrastructure for repository development at the University.

UU wishes to make open science more visible at the grassroots level by learning from the process and the actors' reactions when exposed to ideas of open science and its assessment, and by asking how open science can be made more visible in the existing assets and systems used in research activities (e.g. HRM systems, University profile page, ORCID profile, onboarding materials, and so on). It is anticipated that the tools, services and approaches developed in GraspOS could play an important role in co-creating assessment protocols that seriously consider open science for self-assessment activities.

CNR prioritises debriefing CNR head of management on the pilot findings, but also how the novel indicators and practices as well as the technical infrastructure and services developed within GraspOS can be of assistance in shaping future selections for career progression, and potentially support both applicants in filling in the required documentation and evaluators in criteria definition and evaluation.

UEF wishes to expand its information base used in knowledge management, impact assessment and monitoring open science to less used indicators and metrics, as well as promote and enable open science by exploring and assessing possibilities to utilise less used indicators and metrics of publishing activities for example in recognizing merits in open science.

For UB, the pilot ambitions refer to the development of Cherry and its information base to better enable rewarding not only researchers but also departments on open science activities.

The maturity level of UU in terms of acknowledging open science practices in research assessment is high, and this is also reflected in their identified challenge in developing new ways of evaluating open science: it is possible that they do not need to implement any new research information tools, services or infrastructures, instead potential needs may rather relate to changing processes, developing internal guidelines and protocols for assessment.

UEF considers the lack of evidence for potential benefits of research assessment reform as well as the lack of institutional autonomy due to rules and regulations imposed by research funding organisations as the main barriers to realising the reform on research assessment. In terms of developing new ways of evaluating or monitoring open science, UEF anticipates that the different needs as well as publication cultures of different disciplines is the biggest challenge.

For UB, the biggest challenges have to do with realising their goal of increasing the number of green open access publications in Cherry, as currently only approximately 10 percent of restricted access versions of publications are accepted versions with embargo access. And even with comprehensive training on OS to engage researchers more, authors face limitations in claiming accepted manuscripts, mainly due to not being the primary authors or having previously published the work.

7.3. Pilots supporting OS-aware RA for thematic disciplines

For CS, the motivation to develop new ways to evaluate and monitor open science as well as taking part in GraspOS is to advance a better OS-based RA that better reflects the already

strong OS culture of the CS domain. These development ambitions relate to three main aspects: criteria for research assessment, relevant monitoring mechanisms and discipline-specific prioritisation on tools development.

For OPERAS, it is a similar situation: the aim is to include new research practices relevant for SSH fields that are not being considered enough currently in research assessment. OPERAS expects that through GraspOS a stable federation of RA practices can be established to facilitate the career evaluation of scientists in different domains and to better consider the differences between the roles that a scientist might have in their career. Key to the OPERAS pilot and its ambitions within the SSH domain is to identify qualitative indicators and supplement the quantitative ones used in research assessment currently.

For INRAE, their institutional Open Science Policy is monitored by the national open science dashboard giving an institutional level view. The aim is that on an institutional level INRAE could compare itself with other institutions working in the same scientific domains globally, and on an individual level researchers could have openness and FAIRness profiles. The INRAE pilot supporting OS-aware RA for agricultural and veterinary science is about building new indicators on FAIRness, interdisciplinarity and reproducibility as well as about better understanding the processes of interdisciplinarity and the impact openness has on it. Being clear about what is the added value of participating in GraspOS is not easy at this early stage, but INRAE hopes that the project will help develop and standardise practices, tools, indicators and methods to allow comparisons. From INRAE's point of view the biggest challenge is understanding what is relevant and feasible in the context of GraspOS.

OPERAS mentions as a challenge the lack of data that can be used in research assessment, especially in the context of GDPR rules and regulations.

7.4. Summary of the relevance of the tools and services

The pilots were asked to indicate in the table if the presented GraspOS tools, services and datasets could be interesting for them. The pilots were to briefly describe relevant use case scenarios and include special requirements for these tools, services and datasets that could

be important for the pilot. Some pilots were not able to indicate their potential interest at this early stage of the project. The table below indicates potential relevance based on the pilots' analyses, it does not include use case scenarios or requirements. Detailed descriptions of the GraspOS tools/services and datasets listed in the table can be found in Annex 2.

Table 1. *Relevance of the GraspOS tools and services*

GraspOS service: Enrichment of research outputs with missing attributes	
Component	Potential relevance for pilots
<u>OpenAIRE Broker</u> License: AGPL TRL (start/end): 9/9 Partners: OpenAIRE, CNR	INRAE Research.fi U. Belgrade
<u>OpenAIRE IIS text mining modules</u> License: AGPL TRL (start/end): 9/9 Partners: OpenAIRE, ARC	U. Belgrade
<u>OpenAIRE Metadata Validator</u> License: AGPL TRL (start/end): 7/9 Partners: OpenAIRE	Research.fi U. Belgrade
<u>SCRE Pipeline</u> License: AGPL TRL (start/end): 9/9 Partners: OPERAS	INRAE
GraspOS service: Enrichment of research output links	
Component	Potential relevance for pilots
<u>Semantic Citation Classifier</u> License: MIT TRL (start/end): 4/7 Partner: UNIBO	INRAE U. Belgrade
<u>BIP! citation classifier</u> License: GNU/GPL TRL (start/end): 3/7	INRAE U. Belgrade UEF

<i>Partner: ARC</i>	
GraspOS service: Enrichment of research outputs with novel metrics	
Component	Potential relevance for pilots
EC KIP OS indicators <i>License: GNU/GPL</i> <i>TRL: (start/end): 6/9</i> <i>Partner: ARC</i>	UEF UEFISCDI
<u>BIP! Services (Toolbox)</u> <i>License: GNU/GPL</i> <i>TRL (start/end): 9/9</i> <i>Partner: ARC</i>	INRAE CNR Research.fi U. Belgrade UEF UEFISCDI
GraspOS service: Enrichment of research outputs with usage data	
Component	Potential relevance for pilots
EOSC accounting for services <i>License: Apache</i> <i>TRL (start/end): 5/7</i> <i>Partner: GRNET</i>	U. Belgrade
<u>UsageCounts</u> <i>License: AGPL</i> <i>TRL (start/end): 9/9</i> <i>Partner: OpenAIRE</i>	INRAE CNR U. Belgrade UEFISCDI
<u>OPERAS Metrics</u> <i>License: MIT</i> <i>TRL (start/end): 7/9</i> <i>Partner: OPERAS</i>	CNR U. Belgrade
GraspOS service: OS Institutional Dashboard	
Component	Potential relevance for pilots

OpenAIRE Institutional Monitor Dashboard License: AGPL TRL (start/end): 9/9 Partner: OpenAIRE	INRAE CNR U. Belgrade
GraspOS service: EOSC OS Researcher Dashboard	
Component	Potential relevance for pilots
BIP! Scholar License: GNU/GPL TRL (start/end): 7/9 Partner: ARC	INRAE CNR Research.fi UEF UEFISCDI
GraspOS resource: Scholarly resources	
Resource	Potential relevance for pilots
OpenAIRE Graph Partner: OpenAIRE	Research.fi U. Belgrade
OpenCitations Partner: UNIBO	Research.fi
Scholexplorer Partner: OpenAIRE	Research.fi U. Belgrade
BIP! DB Partner: ARC	Research.fi UEF
OpenAIRE Usage Counts Partner: OpenAIRE	U. Belgrade
OPERAS Metrics Partners: OPERAS	
FAIRCORE4EOSC RAiD Partners: CWTS, OpenAIRE, CSC	INRAE Research.fi

8. Conclusions

Pilots' local state of affairs. In the first section of the analysis, the pilots described what their current situation is in regard to OS and RA practices. The analyses show that the pilots have very different roles: they are evaluating, being evaluated, monitoring, monitoring evaluations, as well as collecting and disseminating information. In terms of evaluating or monitoring open science it is a similarly diverse field from not considering open science in research assessment at all to rewarding and recognising open science in all domains. The maturity level is also different, as for some pilots it is the first time or indeed the initiation for including open science in assessment criteria, but for others openness is a long-standing tradition.

The pilots operate on different levels, national, institutional and disciplinary levels. This is reflected in their operational framework, in what kinds of policies or guidelines define open science and research assessment for the pilots. It is also reflected in their operational environment, in what kinds of developments have an effect on the pilots activities and who are the dominant actors within that space. For the pilots operating on a national level, their activities are guided by national level policies and actors, and for pilots operating on an institutional level, while national level policies and actors are considered relevant, institutional ones are more influential. For pilots operating on a disciplinary level, disciplinary traditions and domain specific issues and development needs are considered as the most important framework for their activities. In other words, pilots describe their operational framework and environment from the point of view of at which level they consider having most influence. What is noteworthy, however, is that the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment is considered as a powerful influence for all pilots, regardless of the level they operate in.

Evaluation context. In the second section of the analysis, the pilots describe their context in terms of evaluation or monitoring. Again, the pilots have very different contexts, reflecting their roles as evaluators or targets of evaluation, as actors supporting or enabling evaluation, or developing evaluation practices. They also have a variety of stakeholders, ranging from relevant ministries and policy makers to research performing and funding organisations, institutional level senior management, researchers, publishers and editors, and research infrastructure professionals. So it can be said that with the nine pilots, GraspOS is able to cover the research community as a whole.

Which open science practices are evaluated is in general defined on the level the pilot is operating on, i.e. national, institutional or disciplinary level, but the reasons why open science

is evaluated seem to be similar for all pilots, regardless of their operational level: for raising awareness of open science and its benefits, following up on developments in open science, identifying development needs, and being able to reward and recognise open science practices and activities.

Pilot ambitions. In the last section of the analysis, the pilots describe the reasons for evaluating open science, what they want to develop in this respect, and why, and finally what the pilots think GraspOS has to offer them. All pilots have similar ambitions in terms of OS-aware RA. They wish to expand the types of research outputs and activities for a more diverse and comprehensive view on the contributions researchers bring to open scholarship and science in general. Supporting the transition towards realising the commitments of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment is also a joint ambition, as is rewarding open science activities.

As benefits of participating in GraspOS the pilots mention international cooperation in discussing why open science should be evaluated or monitored and designing mutually acceptable ways to do that. Developing practices, tools, indicators and methods to allow comparisons as well as developing indicators for new types of activities currently overlooked in general assessment practices are also mentioned, as well as supporting the implementation of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment.

Challenges. As the last supporting question in the analysis, the pilots were asked to consider the challenges involved in developing new ways of evaluating or monitoring open science. Regardless of the level of operation, the pilots' challenges are shared, and mostly have to do with the lack of comprehensive and reliable information on open science activities, which results in a lack of appropriate indicators and metrics. Also lack of supporting infrastructure is considered a challenge, for example in terms of linking different types of information or ensuring data interoperability, as well as lack of clear guidelines on how to use new types of information when it is collected which translates to challenges in terms of transparency and predictability of assessment. There are concerns over the ambiguous nature of open science especially in terms of how activities and merits in open science not currently available could be captured in a reliable way. Or, vice versa, concerns over general assessment practices not acknowledging a diversity of research practices already traditional in some domains. The challenges mentioned by the pilots also included the lack of evidence of the benefits of reforming research assessment, as well as lack of institutional autonomy due to rules and regulations imposed by external actors, such as research funders, both of which can manifest as resistance to change. And finally, the pilots raised the challenges caused by the different

needs and publication cultures of different disciplines that need to be taken into account in reforming research assessment.

To conclude, the pilots represent a wide variety of stakeholders providing GraspOS an opportunity to develop indicators, tools, services and infrastructure applied in assessment or monitoring based on real community needs. The pilots have a shared understanding of what open science aware research assessment means, as well as of the development needs and challenges to do with new ways of evaluating or monitoring open science. In addition they are all committed to realising the commitments of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment.

9. References

Hyrkkänen, A-K., Ivanovic, D., Pölönen, J., Kari, M., & Pylvänäinen, E. (2023) GraspOS Deliverable 2.1: OS-aware RRA approaches landscape report (Draft).

10. Annexes

1. Template for pilot analysis
2. GraspOS Tools/Services descriptions

Annex 1. Template for the pilot analysis

Introduction

This analysis is conducted to describe the current status of the pilot's research evaluation aims, context, and resources. The analysis:

- a) establishes the pilot's ambitions and level of maturity towards research assessment reform,
- b) collects contextually relevant information to facilitate shaping of the pilot evaluation event focused on open science practices (supporting WP2), and
- c) provides information on the initial requirements and the current best practices for indicators, data, tools and services (supporting WP3 and WP4).

The analysis has three parts. The pilots will describe:

1) Pilot's state of affairs in terms of

- 1.a) Open Science & Research Assessment practices
- 1.b) Tools/services and datasets used
- 1.c) Gaps

2) Evaluation context

3) Pilot ambitions in terms of developing new ways of evaluating/monitoring open science

Instructions on using the template

The template includes supporting questions under each section. However, as the pilots are diverse in their needs and vision, as well as their level of maturity in relation to research assessment reform and infrastructure, pilots can choose which of these questions are relevant to their setting. The aim of this analysis is not to rush the pilots into making quick decisions in regard to open science aware research assessment and how it should be conducted in the future, instead it is aimed at supporting the pilots in identifying their current status and future ambitions.

Please use the headings provided in the template to structure your analysis.

Please use the tables provided in the template. Other sections are free text questions.

The analysis should be uploaded to the GraspOS Google Drive directory folder titled Pilot analyses in word format:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1zyCJq-2S6k7PnOHrSpp06ReChZUtc2FY?usp=share_link

The deadline for the analysis is 14 July, 2023, EOD.

More practical instructions will be provided in the upcoming monthly meetings for WP5 (to be scheduled later in March).

Please check the goals and links to GraspOS as well as the KPIs listed in the proposal, and update them if necessary.

Goals & links to GraspOS	from the proposal	updates if needed
KPIs	from the proposal	updates if needed

1. Local state of affairs

a) Open science and/or research assessment (free text question)

SUPPORTING QUESTIONS to consider if relevant:

- In the context of your pilot, what does open science (OS) aware research assessment (RA) mean? How are OS practices considered and acknowledged in RA at the moment?
- What is the pilot's operational framework in terms of OS and/or RA: what kinds of policies, guidelines, principles, and/or best practices are there that refer to OS and/or RA (nationally, institutionally, within a discipline, whatever is the relevant level for the pilot)?
- What is the pilot's operational environment in terms of OS and/or RA: what kinds of developments are going on at the moment within the pilot's context, and how is the pilot connected to those developments? Does the pilot have access (influence) to these developments?
- The dominant practices within OS and/or RA: who or what are the dominant actors, i.e., who is in charge, what are the dominant practices, where and how is OS and/or RA defined and/or developed, and what is the level of awareness of OS and/or responsible research assessment (RRA) within the dominant practices and/or actors? Can you identify current RA practices that are not responsible?

b) Tools, services and data used

Instructions: Please use the table to list the targets of evaluation or monitoring, and the tools, services or data sources used. Also list any challenges you may have encountered using different tools, services or data sources.

Target of assessment/monitoring	Tools, services used *)	Data source(s) **)	Challenges ***)

*) indicators, metrics, monitoring tools (dashboards, PowerBI, aggregations, etc.), services supporting calculations, implementation, different templates (portfolio, cv, narratives, etc)

***) include also if they are internal or external, national or international, if there are issues with quality of data, etc.

***) limitations, restrictions, openness to interpretations, etc. to do with tools, services and/or data sources used

SUPPORTING QUESTIONS to consider if relevant:

(free text question)

- Is there a current research information system (CRIS) in use, and if so, is it:
 - Pure, Converis, Symplectic Elements, or some other solution?
 - in-house solution?
- Is there an institutional repository (for publications), if not which repositories are you suggesting/using
- How is your infrastructure linked to the EU/EOSC?
- Is there a personnel management system?
- Is there a researcher profile system or some tools to create online CVs and/or academic profiles?
- Are there other local platforms in use?
- Is there support/information on OS available
- Are there research practices that touch upon FAIR or open data, or software?

c) What are you missing currently in terms of tools, services, data (indicators, metrics, quality, protocols, practices,...)? (free text question)

2. Evaluation Context (free text question)

SUPPORTING QUESTIONS to consider if relevant:

- What is the broader function of research evaluation for this pilot context? For example, in what ways do research evaluation events link to collective values (e.g in a mission statement or research agenda, or in normative practices)?
- Who are the intended stakeholders, audience(s), and beneficiaries for the outcome of the pilot evaluation?
- Which contextual factors are relevant for shaping the research evaluation criteria and content (e.g. level of analysis, institutional structures, disciplinary structures, etc.)
- Who are the key actors (by title) in preparing and conducting this pilot evaluation event?

Relevance of practices

Are the following relevant to monitoring OS in your setting? Are they relevant to research evaluation for researchers or your organisation?

Instructions: Please indicate which (if any) of the following open practices are considered or acknowledged in monitoring and/or evaluation within the pilot setting. Also, indicate on which types of OS activity (e.g., outputs, usage, practices) data is collected. Add new rows if necessary.

	Monitoring	Research evaluation
<i>Open practices considered/acknowledged in monitoring and/or evaluation</i>		

<i>FAIRness</i>		
<i>Reproducibility</i>		
<i>Interdisciplinarity</i>		
<i>Research Outputs usages</i>		
<i>Collaboration</i>		
<i>Other practices</i> [please add rows if needed]		
<i>Data collected or used for monitoring and/or evaluating OS</i>		
<i>Open research outputs</i> [E.g., which research results are relevant? Publications, data, software, services, tools, other? Is FAIR data important in monitoring or assessment in your setting? If yes, how is it captured? Are you using assessment tools? Does institutional/national repository offer FAIR by design /default?]		
<i>Links among research outcomes</i> [E.g., for monitoring: does it make any sense on how objects are linked together. E.g., provenance]		
<i>Usage of research outcomes</i> [E.g., is usage (clicks/downloads, citations) taken into account in monitoring/assessment? If yes, how? If yes, how do you have access to these?]		
<i>Usage of services</i> [E.g., EOSC is keen on publishing and sharing services. How important is this for monitoring research or open science in your environment?]		

<p>Data on practising OS [E.g., researchers practice OS in many ways that are not captured by OA/FAIR infrastructure. E.g., data stewardship, citizen engagement, open source community software. What other practices do you, or would you like to measure? How do you record these?]</p>		
<p>Other [please add rows if necessary]</p>		

3. **Pilot ambitions** in terms of developing new ways of evaluating/monitoring open science (free text question)

SUPPORTING QUESTIONS to consider if relevant:

- Why evaluate OS: what does the pilot use the evaluation/monitoring of OS for at the moment, and what the pilot hopes to use it for in the future?
- What does the pilot want to develop and why: what is valued, i.e., what would be evaluated/monitored, and how could/should it be evaluated/monitored?
- Gap analysis between what the pilot wants to develop and what are the dominant practices: what do you think you CAN change, and how? How can GraspOS support here, i.e., what is the value proposition to dominant actors and practices to cooperate with GraspOS. What is the added value of being a part of the project?
- Do you anticipate some challenges or barriers involved in developing new ways of evaluating/monitoring open science (to do with, for example, lack of data or information, lack of indicators, issues to do with local privacy regulations, etc.)?

Considering how GraspOS tools/services (WP3) and datasets (WP4) may be helpful

Instructions: Please indicate in the second column of the next table which GraspOS tools/services and datasets could be interesting for your pilot by briefly describing relevant use case scenarios (no obligation to use them is implied - just expression of relevance/interest). In addition, please include in the third column some special requirements for these tools/services or datasets that may be important for your pilot. Detailed descriptions for all GraspOS tools/services and datasets can be found in Appendix A. If a tool/service or dataset seems to be irrelevant to your use cases just leave blank the respective cell.

GraspOS service: Enrichment of research outputs with missing attributes

Component	Usage scenarios	Requirements
OpenAIRE Broker License: AGPL TRL (start/end): 9/9 Partners: OpenAIRE, CNR		
OpenAIRE IIS text mining modules License: AGPL TRL (start/end): 9/9 Partners: OpenAIRE, ARC		
OpenAIRE Metadata Validator License: AGPL TRL (start/end): 7/9 Partners: OpenAIRE		
SCRE Pipeline License: AGPL TRL (start/end): 9/9 Partners: OPERAS		
GrasPOS service: Enrichment of research output links		
Component	Usage scenario	Requirements
Semantic Citation Classifier License: MIT TRL (start/end): 4/7 Partner: UNIBO		
BIP! citation classifier License: GNU/GPL TRL (start/end): 3/7 Partner: ARC		
GrasPOS service: Enrichment of research outputs with novel metrics		
Component	Usage scenarios	Requirements
EC KIP OS indicators License: GNU/GPL TRL: (start/end): 6/9 Partner: ARC		
BIP! Services (Toolbox) License: GNU/GPL		

TRL (start/end): 9/9 Partner: ARC		
GrasOS service: Enrichment of research outputs with usage data		
Component	Usage scenarios	Requirements
EOSC accounting for services License: Apache TRL (start/end): 5/7 Partner: GRNET		
UsageCounts License: AGPL TRL (start/end): 9/9 Partner: OpenAIRE		
OPERAS Metrics License: MIT TRL (start/end): 7/9 Partner: OPERAS		
GrasOS service: OS Institutional Dashboard		
Component	Usage scenarios	Requirements
OpenAIRE Institutional Monitor Dashboard License: AGPL TRL (start/end): 9/9 Partner: OpenAIRE		
GrasOS service: EOSC OS Researcher Dashboard		
Component	Usage scenarios	Requirements
BIP! Scholar License: GNU/GPL TRL (start/end): 7/9 Partner: ARC		
GrasOS resource: Scholarly resources		
Resource	Usage scenarios	Requirements
OpenAIRE Graph Partner: OpenAIRE		
OpenCitations		

<i>Partner: UNIBO</i>		
Scholexplorer <i>Partner: OpenAIRE</i>		
BIP! DB <i>Partner: ARC</i>		
OpenAIRE Usage Counts <i>Partner: OpenAIRE</i>		
OPERAS Metrics <i>Partners: OPERAS</i>		
FAIRCORE4EOSC RAiD <i>Partners: CWTS, OpenAIRE, CSC</i>		

Annex 2. GraspOS Tools/Services descriptions

GraspOS service: Enrichment of research outputs with missing attributes		
Component	Description	GraspOS extensions
OpenAIRE Broker License: AGPL TRL (start/end): 9/9 Partners: OpenAIRE, CNR	A subscription-notification service that enables content providers (repositories, CRIS systems, aggregators, knowledge graphs, publishers) to enrich content with additional metadata. It utilises the OpenAIRE Graph has a key role in the de-centralization and local re-use of all metadata available.	Extend current data model to cover additional research results, relationships between products, classifications, and other metrics included in metadata records.
OpenAIRE IIS text mining modules License: AGPL TRL (start/end): 9/9 Partners: OpenAIRE, ARC	An information inference service that enriches scholarly data with automatically inferred metadata, based on a flexible big data processing pipeline supporting full-text and metadata mining. Current modules include citation extraction (article-data, article-software, product-grant, product-organisations); subject inference (Frascati and SDG); community context.	Extend with methods for the completeness of metadata (e.g., resource types, subjects, licensing typology) and, in particular for the pilots, deeper classifications (>Frascati Level 4) to be used in capturing discipline specific characteristics.
OpenAIRE Metadata Validator License: AGPL TRL (start/end): 7/9 Partners: OpenAIRE	A rule-based service that provides metrics on FAIR assessment of content providers (data, software, publication repositories/journals, CRIS systems) based on metadata of the research objects.	Extend with configurations for custom and domain-specific FAIRness metrics at the level of the individual records and average-based metrics for data sources, funders, institutions. Publish as a stand-alone service (now embedded in PROVIDE Dashboard).
SCRE Pipeline License: AGPL TRL (start/end): 9/9 Partners: OPERAS	A general and configurable AI-assisted content acquisition and processing pipeline for documents and projects that aggregates and performs data cleaning and semantic processing.	Extend with methods for the completeness of metadata for SSH. Upgrade so outputs match the specifications from RDA IG Scientific Knowledge Graphs.
GraspOS service: Enrichment of research output links		
Component	Description	GraspOS extensions

<p>Semantic Citation Classifier License: MIT TRL (start/end): 4/7 Partner: UNIBO</p>	<p>A tool that performs automatic annotation of citations in academic papers, by processing bibliographic data and the text in which the citation appears. It enriches each individual citation with structural and semantic features combining deep learning and problem reduction techniques.</p>	<p>Extended to detect a larger set of citation intents. We will extend the training dataset and refine the classification techniques used so far in order increase accuracy and coverage of domains. New data fusion techniques will also be implemented - for instance, the reduction to Semantic Retrieval (SR). Multi-faceted classification will also be explored, and we will build a more flexible and robust module to export citation data and link them to existing datasets.</p>
<p>BIP! citation classifier License: GNU/GPL TRL (start/end): 3/7 Partner: ARC</p>	<p>A tool that automatically annotates citations based on their intent.</p>	<p>Currently the tool is focussed on CS publications, the plan is to be extended for other fields.</p>
<p>GraspOS service: Enrichment of research outputs with novel metrics</p>		
<p>Component</p>	<p>Description</p>	<p>GraspOS extensions</p>
<p>EC KIP OS indicators License: GNU/GPL TRL: (start/end): 6/9 Partner: ARC</p>	<p>A suite of advanced software components for indicators on impact and collaboration of OA based research outputs on citation and network analysis (with emphasis where possible on timeliness): Field-Weighted Citation Impact - FWCI scores, Collaborative Index (CI), Degree of collaboration (DC), Collaborative coefficient (CC).</p>	<p>Extend to offer aggregate metrics for funders, research groups and institutions and with models that cover additional research products, not just publications. Use pilots for benchmarking and further extensions.</p>
<p>BIP! Services (Toolbox) License: GNU/GPL TRL (start/end): 9/9 Partner: ARC</p>	<p>A suite of advanced software components that leverages scholarly knowledge graphs (Crossref, OpenCitations, OpenAIRE Graph) and produces advanced citation-based indicators for publications and researchers that capture popularity (= short-term impact), influence (= long-term impact), impulse (= initial momentum).</p>	<p>Extend to offer aggregate metrics to research groups and institutions and to provide additional metrics that will cover (a) EOSC service usage and (b) the level, impact, collaboration, and timeliness in OS practice for researchers, groups, and institutions.</p>
<p>GraspOS service: Enrichment of research outputs with usage data</p>		

Component	Description	GraspOS extensions
EOSC accounting for services <i>License: Apache</i> <i>TRL (start/end): 5/7</i> <i>Partner: GRNET</i>	A tool that collects service metrics such as Virtual Access Metrics and aggregates them according to EOSC/community rules. It would be used as a data source for impact metrics for the services as part of the federated metrics infrastructure.	Extend with an add-on and APIs to provide aggregate level metrics and reports.
UsageCounts <i>License: AGPL</i> <i>TRL (start/end): 9/9</i> <i>Partner: OpenAIRE</i>	A service that collects usage data from OS content providers repositories, journals, and other scientific data sources. Using COUNTER code aggregates, deduplicates and delivers standardised activity reports (SUSHI) about research usage and uptake. Offers data collection from MakeDataCount.	Extend with an add-on and APIs to provide metrics and reports for funders, organisations and individual researchers. Be the key technology in the OA Trust eBook and the IDS prototype.
OPERAS Metrics <i>License: MIT</i> <i>TRL (start/end): 7/9</i> <i>Partner: OPERAS</i>	The service collects usage and alternative metrics for OA monographs and books: downloads, web visits, tweets, wikipedia mentions, etc. It is based on a shared data model	Extend with an add-on and APIs to provide aggregate level metrics and reports, accommodating also OA journal articles.
GraspOS service: OS Institutional Dashboard		
Component	Description	GraspOS extensions
OpenAIRE Institutional Monitor Dashboard <i>License: AGPL</i> <i>TRL (start/end): 9/9</i> <i>Partner: OpenAIRE</i>	A service built on the OpenAIRE Research Graph providing monitoring services for research output of research actors. The service offers OS statistics focusing on products, funders, and sub-units of a given institution. It is highly configurable to accommodate mix & match indicators and metrics.	Extend with additional indicators. Enhance the existing administration backend with pre-set templates and support others for building additional ones tailored to their needs.
GraspOS service: EOSC OS Researcher Dashboard		
Component	Description	GraspOS extensions

<p>BIP! Scholar License: GNU/GPL TRL (start/end): 7/9 Partner: ARC</p>	<p>A dashboard that leverages data from scholarly knowledge graphs (OpenAIRE Graph Crossref, OpenCitations) and ORCID to display custom reports containing a variety of researcher-level RRA indicators for researchers capturing different aspects of their performance (e.g., productivity, impact, career stage) while considering the different roles of researchers in the respective works (according to the CRediT taxonomy).</p>	<p>Extend to provide detailed reports on researchers' OS practice (level and impact). The reports will include intuitive visualisations and will cover also groups of researchers</p>
<p>GraspOS resource: Scholarly resources</p>		
<p>Resource</p>		
<p>OpenAIRE Graph Partner: OpenAIRE</p>	<p>A service that populates and provides access to a scientific knowledge graph that includes metadata and links between scientific products, organizations, funders, funding streams, projects, communities, and (provenance) data sources.</p>	
<p>OpenCitations Partner: UNIBO</p>	<p>An infrastructure provided by a not-for-profit organization that publishes open bibliographic and citation data by the use of Linked Data technologies. Its main Index (COCI) currently contains more than 1.29M citation links</p>	
<p>Scholexplorer Partner: OpenAIRE</p>	<p>A service that populates and provides access to a graph of links between dataset and literature objects and dataset and dataset objects.</p>	
<p>BIP! DB Partner: ARC</p>	<p>A dataset that contains citation-based impact indicators for more than 138M articles considering a citation network that consists of more than 1.672B citations.</p>	
<p>OpenAIRE Usage Counts Partner: OpenAIRE</p>	<p>A dataset containing usage data for various types of research products (e.g., publications, datasets, etc).</p>	
<p>OPERAS Metrics Partners: OPERAS</p>	<p>The service collects usage and alternative metrics for OA monographs and books: downloads, web visits, tweets, wikipedia mentions, etc. It is based on a shared data model.</p>	
<p>FAIRCORE4EOSC RAiD Partners: CWTS, OpenAIRE, CSC</p>	<p>A resource collecting research activity identifiers (i.e., research projects), implemented as an EOSC-integrated service in the context of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project.</p>	